

CURING STRAINS DEVELOPED DURING THE MANUFACTURE OF GRP TUBES

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SUMMARY: During the manufacture of glass reinforced plastic tubes it should be recognised that the matrix can undergo significant chemical shrinkage. It has been shown that the shrinkage due to post-cure at elevated temperatures could cause strains of significant magnitudes that could exceed the levels of stress or strain allowed for by accepted design codes and are sufficient to promote environmentally assisted cracking in certain operating environments. However, in the cases presented, no consideration was given to the strains developed during the actual lay-up of individual layers. This work provides some experimental results showing that high extension hoop and longitudinal shrinkage strains are developed during the lay-up of thick tubes layers. It is also shown that the post-cure alleviates the hoop strains to acceptable levels while the longitudinal strains are increased to possibly unacceptable magnitudes.

KEYWORDS: glass reinforced plastic, GRP, tubes, curing shrinkage, cure, post-cure

INTRODUCTION

Glass reinforced plastic (GRP) is an ideal material of choice for the manufacture of many items of chemical plant equipment. Its ability to resist degradation in aggressive chemical environments is one of the major benefits. However, the material is prone to environmentally assisted cracking (EAC) if the tensile stresses in the exposed material are not kept low. This is well recognised by codes of practice for the design of GRP equipment, which ensure specification of geometry's leading to low stresses in response to mechanical loading. Other sources of stress are also important, e.g. thermal, process induced. It has been shown that, when polyester and vinyl ester resins, typical of those used in process plant applications, are subject to elevated temperature post-cure after room temperature polymerisation, significant chemical shrinkage can occur [1, 2]. It has been presented that since this shrinkage occurs with the matrix already gelled, any restraint can give rise to large residual stresses, in particular tensile surface stresses of sufficient magnitude promote environmentally assisted cracking in many environments. However, no consideration was given to the strains developed during the actual lay-up of the individual layers. These strains are of primary importance for the determination of residual stresses and strains after manufacture. Although these shrinkage residual stresses are clearly important to designers of chemical process equipment, only limited experimental work appears to have been carried out to date. The aim of this work is to present experimental results for the shrinkage strains during manufacture, lay-up and post-cure, of typical materials and also for tubes of practical dimension. These results are compared to theoretical predictions.

CURING STRAINS DEVELOPED IN A TUBE DURING LAY-UP OF LAYERS

Two identical tubes with internal diameters of 50 mm, were manufactured on an expandable mandrel from DION 9100/CSM with a glass content of 28%. After the lay-up and cure of the surface tissue, two strain gauges were attached to each of the surface tissues to measure the hoop and longitudinal strains during lay-up of the body of the tubes. Four layers per day were applied by hand lay-up to minimise steep temperature gradients resulting from exotherm while continuously recording the strains developed due to curing. A wall thickness of ± 15 mm was obtained from sixteen layers with a tube length of 240 mm. The recorded strains were plotted to the number of layers.

Results and Discussion

The curves shown in Fig. 1 and Fig. 2 represent the strains recorded during the actual lay-up of the layers of tubes 1 and 2.

Fig. 1: Longitudinal & Hoop curing strains vs. layers for DION 9100/CSM tube (1) at inside surface

Fig. 2: Longitudinal & Hoop curing strains vs. layers for DION 9100/CSM tube (2) at inside surface

The peaks shown before layer 3 in both the figures indicate when the tubes were released from the mandrels. It can be seen that a maximum extension hoop strain of $1629\mu\epsilon$ and a longitudinal shrinkage strain of $-1181\mu\epsilon$ was attained during the lay-up of the layers for tube

1, and a maximum extension hoop strain of $1508\mu\epsilon$ and a longitudinal shrinkage strain of $-1248\mu\epsilon$ for tube 2.

Although the figures indicate that exotherm did play a role in the variation in strains, the zero and the maximum strain values were obtained at 18°C . Fig. 3 shows the temperature variation of the inner surface due to exotherm during the lay-up of the layers. It is shown that a variation of approximately 6°C is given by any layer for the given thickness of the tube. Values of curing strains for the two tubes are given in Table 1.

Fig. 3. Temperature variation of tube (1) inner surface due to exotherm

Table 1. Curing strains at the inner surface

Gauge Position & Direction	Strain Measured $\times 10^{-6}$	
	Tube (1)	Tube (2)
Inside Hoop (ϵ_{iz})	1629	1508
Inside Longitudinal (ϵ_{iy})	-1181	-1248

DETERMINATION OF INNER HOOP STRAIN DUE TO CURE DURING LAY-UP

Interpreting the results, in particular the “growth” of the inner circumference, the following observation is made:

1. immediately after the lay-up of layer n ($n=1, 2..16$), the laminate expands due to the heat generated by the exothermic reaction of layer n ;
2. layer n bonds to the laminate and after the exothermic reaction has been completed the whole system cools to ambient temperature;
3. as the system returns to ambient temperature, layer n prevents it to return to its original size and hence a “growth” of the inner circumference is shown and residual strains are produced.

In support of this observation calculations were made by using expressions given by Roy and Kim [3]. Material properties of the DION 9100/CSM tubes used in this study were

determined from methods given by Hoa [4] using $E_m = 3.5$ GPa, $E_f = 72$ GPa, $\nu_m = 0.35$, $\nu_f = 0.2$, $\nu_m = 0.8$, $\alpha_m = 73\mu\epsilon$ and $\alpha_f = 5\mu\epsilon$, where α_m and α_f are the coefficient of expansions (CTEs) of the matrix and the glass mat respectively. The calculated material properties are shown in Table 2 where subscripts z , r and θ indicate the axial, radial and tangential directions respectively. However, the expression for hoop thermal strains for a change in temperature does not take the change in thickness due to lay-up into account. Therefore the addition of the layers (n) were incorporated for strain calculations:

$$\begin{aligned} \epsilon_{\theta h_n} = \epsilon_{\theta c_n} = & \frac{(\alpha_r - \alpha_\theta)(k^2 - \nu_{r\theta}^2)}{(1 - k^2)(1 - c^{2k})} \left[\frac{c_n^{k+1} - 1}{k + \nu_{r\theta}} \left(\frac{r}{b_n} \right)^{k-1} + \frac{c_n^{k+1} - c_n^{2k}}{k - \nu_{r\theta}} \left(\frac{b_n}{r} \right)^{k+1} \right] \Delta T \dots \\ & + \frac{\alpha_r(1 - \nu_{r\theta}) - \alpha_\theta(k^2 - \nu_{r\theta})}{1 - k^2} \Delta T \end{aligned} \quad (1)$$

where

$$c = \frac{a}{b_n}; \quad b_n = a + n \cdot t; \quad k = \sqrt{\frac{S_{rr}}{S_{\theta\theta}}} \quad \text{and} \quad \nu_{r\theta} = -\frac{S_{r\theta}}{S_{\theta\theta}}$$

with a and b_n being the inner and outer radii of the tube, $S_{r\theta}$ and $S_{\theta\theta}$ the elements of the compliance matrix and α_r and α_θ are the CTEs of the ring in the radial and hoop directions respectively. $\epsilon_{\theta h_n}$ and $\epsilon_{\theta c_n}$ are the strains recorded resulting from the exotherm of layer n and from cooling to ambient temperature respectively and with t being the nominal thickness of each layer. Applying temperature changes due to exotherm of $\Delta T = 6^\circ\text{C}$ and a cooling temperature of -6°C , the strains are calculated for layers $n = 1, 2..16$. The strain at the inner surface of the tube, resulting from the curing of the matrix during the lay-up of the individual layers, was then calculated by:

$$\epsilon_\theta = \sum_{n=1}^{15} \epsilon_{\theta h_n} + \sum_{n=2}^{16} \epsilon_{\theta c_n} \quad (2)$$

with no usable results although the results do show that a “growth” actually occurs. It was, however found that if the expansion, determined for $n = 1$, is multiplied by n , reasonable results are obtained. Fig. 4 shows a linear fit of the actual hoop strain recorded and predicted results using $\epsilon_\theta = n \cdot \epsilon_{\theta h_1}$, at the inner surface. This gives a hoop strain at the inner surface of $+1432\mu\epsilon$ which corresponds well with the experimental values given in Table 1.

Table 2. Material Properties of DION 9100/CSM Laminates

Material Property	DION 9100/CSM
$E_{zz} = E_{\theta\theta}$	7120 MPa
E_{rr}	5125 MPa
$E_{r\theta}$	2337 MPa
$\nu_{z\theta}$	0.0954
$\nu_{zr} = \nu_{r\theta}$	0.32
$\alpha_z = \alpha_\theta$	16.07 $\mu\epsilon$
α_r	74.89 $\mu\epsilon$

Fig. 4. Actual and predicted hoop curing strains vs. layers for DION 9100/CSM tube at the inner surface

POST-CURE SHRINKAGE OF CSM/VINYL ESTER TUBE

The two tubes were machined down to a wall thickness of 13.5 mm and prepared for post-cure by attaching two additional strain gauges, in the hoop and longitudinal directions, to the outer surface. The tubes were then placed in an oven and heated gradually to a maximum post-curing temperature of 90°C during which the strains resulting from thermal expansion and chemical shrinkage were recorded.

Results and Discussion

Fig. 5 and Fig. 6 show the strains recorded on the tubes during the post-curing process. The tubes expanded as a result of the increase in temperature until approximately 45°C at which post-cure shrinkage commenced. The tubes were maintained at maximum temperature for 2½ hours and then cooled to room temperature. The shrinkage strains measured are given in Table 3 [1, 5].

Fig. 5. Longitudinal & Hoop post-cure strains vs. temperature for DION 9100/CSM tube (1) on inside surface

Fig. 6. Longitudinal & Hoop post-cure strains vs. temperature for DION 9100/CSM tube (2) on inside surface

However, it must be kept in mind that, since the initial strains were zeroed at commencement of the post-curing cycle, these strains are real values for the post-curing process and do not include the strains developed during the lay-up phase. Combining the post-curing strains to those obtained during lay-up, the final values obviously will be quite different, as are shown in Fig. 7 and Fig. 8.

Table 4 presents the final strains after the combination of the cure and post-cure strains. From these values a good correlation is found between the longitudinal strains. The hoop strains, however, do not compare well. This is due to the large variation found in the strains produced during the post-curing process.

Fig. 7. Actual Post-cure Longitudinal & Hoop Strains vs. Temperature for DION 9100/CSM tube (1) on inside surface

Fig. 8. Actual Post-cure Longitudinal & Hoop Strains vs. Temperature for DION 9100/CSM tube (2) on inside surface

Table 3. Post-cure shrinkage strains of the DION 9100/CSM tubes

Gauge Position & Direction	Strain Measured $\times 10^{-6}$	
	Tube (1)	Tube (2)
Inside Hoop (ϵ_{iz})	-2719	-1495
Inside Longitudinal (ϵ_{iy})	-1037	-1020

Table 4. Final shrinkage strains of the DION 9100/CSM tubes

Gauge Position & Direction	Strain Measured $\times 10^{-6}$	
	Tube (1)	Tube (2)
Inside Hoop (ϵ_{iz})	-1090	-13
Inside Longitudinal (ϵ_{iy})	-2218	-2268

CONCLUSIONS

It has been shown that significant strains are developed during the actual lay-up of individual layers of the laminate. Longitudinal strains decreased, as would be expected, but the hoop strains increased. By predicting the hoop strains, a constant temperature distribution through the laminate was assumed. However, for the material used, the temperature distribution should be linear, decreasing from the outer to the inner surface. It was also assumed that the curing shrinkage of layer n has no effect on the strain at the inner surface of the tube. These assumptions, together with the prediction of the CTEs, probably contributed to the fact that no usable results were obtained from Eqn 2.

It is also shown that post-curing of GRP tubes play an important role in the alleviation of residual hoop strains. It does however increase the residual longitudinal strains which could enhance EAC resulting from mechanical loading.

It is suggested that further experimentation of this kind is required to formulate acceptable methods to predict the strains developed during manufacture.

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